

Transcript of interview with Fredi Devas, John and Rowan Aitchison

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FD: Fredi Devas

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Introductions

JA: I am John Aitchison. I am a wildlife cameraman. I'm joined by my son Rowan and Fredi Devas. Rowan you tell us just quickly what your situation is.

RA: Hi yes, I'm also a cameraman. I am just starting out in wildlife filmmaking but trying to decide where to go with it and what wildlife filmmaking will look like 10 years from now and if I want to be part of that as an industry.

JA: What about you Fredi?

FD: I've been working with you, John, making wildlife films for the BBC - what are called the landmark series, so generally with David Attenborough narrating them, for the last 14 years, so on series like *Frozen Planet* and *Planet Earth II* and most recently on *Seven Worlds: One Planet*, and in all that time I have been thinking very much about the content of these wildlife series and whether we should be saying more about environmental issues that are impacting the natural world.

JA: Thank you. I think that unites the three of us, doesn't it? So, in essence I'm one of the people who does the filming, you [Fredi] are one of the people who produces the films and decide what's in them to a large extent, and Rowan is someone coming into this. He's 20 years old and is deciding whether or not he feels this is doing enough good, really, which is a question that we share, all of us.

Have we failed to communicate the urgent need for action?

JA: So just to set the scene now, more than half the human population of the world is urban, more than half of us live in cities, and exposure to nature is very good for us but, first-hand, it's increasingly rare and it's obvious to us and becoming more and more obvious to more people, that ecosystem collapse and the climate emergency are combined and entwined together and that they're happening very rapidly. If we want to avert warming above 1.5°C above pre-industrial global temperature and stop ecosystems collapsing around us, we have

to act extremely quickly. As Greta Thunberg put it, our house is on fire, so we have to change our lives drastically and we need to get that information to the public in large numbers and start acting. We know that films are good at that kind of thing but even so the pace of change is still very slow, even though we've been making these wildlife films for many decades. The first thing to think about is that we are supposed to be key communicators about the natural world, so do you think we have failed in that, as documentary makers; failed to impart the urgency and to achieve very much with our films? Sometimes it feels to me that we have failed quite badly, or progress would have been greater in this respect. We would have made more progress towards reducing the amount of CO² in the atmosphere for instance, and we really haven't done that.

Fredi, what do you think about that? Have we failed in our role?

FD: I think that's an interesting word. Could we have done more? Absolutely no question about that. Have we failed? That's a very big question because is it us that's failing, or is it the whole system around mass consumption? I think we could have done a lot, lot more.

I think there are areas that you can say we have failed in; so, as wildlife filmmakers that reach huge numbers of people, have we talked about humans creating a mass extinction event - the 6th mass extinction - and we're at the start of it? Have we communicated that widely? I don't think we have and I think that's a massive thing. Mostly I think we should have done more and we need to keep thinking about what more we can do, because time is running out so much. I mean, that's a deeply emotional question John.

JA: Yes, I think so too and you find that too, don't you Rowan? It's very upsetting isn't it, thinking about this, about where we are and about the situation we are in and what to do about it, and the difficulty of achieving anything?

RA: Yes absolutely, for me looking back on things with 20/20 vision, it does look very close to failing on a lot of the key issues, because I had nothing to do with them [the programmes] in the past, but looking forward the only hope is that we change rather rapidly in the way we do things, to keep up with how it is today, predicting how bad it will get and making programmes with that in mind. By the time the programmes come out they need to be level with the public consensus on how bad it is, to match the urgency as well.

FD: John, you can answer this a bit more, but my perspective is that going back to the '70s and '80s, there was a reasonably strong environmental movement and some really bad environmental films were made which preached and preached, and talked about all the bad

things that were happening, but weren't necessarily inspiring films and you came away feeling bad about yourself, and then what happened with big successful series like *Blue Planet* and *Planet Earth*, is that people were taken away in escapist form, to go and see absolute wilderness; pristine wilderness, beautifully portrayed and wonderful animal behaviour happening within those landscapes. I remember when I first joined the industry being told that there had been a study which showed that people were more likely to give to large charities like WWF after having seen *Planet Earth*, so there was this feeling that these series were really engaging people in the natural world and showing them how much they loved the natural world, and from that they would then find out about causes and act on it. The big question is, did that happen? And what's a shame is, my feeling is, that lots of great films, environmental, inspiring films that are very engaging, have been blocked in the last 15 years because people are scared that they going to turn off viewers, that they're going to get a smaller audience. The filmmaking has been held back a little bit.

You can make powerful films that deal with environmental issues that are so emotional and people want to hear about it, but people were scared of that, so they stopped it and I think that's a real shame.

JA: Yes, I agree with that. I think that's exactly what happened. I think you've hit the nail on the head. In the '70s, when perhaps the news was new that the Amazon was burning for instance, there was a series called *Decade of Destruction*, about the Amazon being destroyed. It was a really difficult thing to watch because it was so grim, but it was actually breaking the news, in a visual way, to more people than usual, that this was going on, but I think the effect was that the audiences for those hard hitting programmes were rather low and when you set that against a big, successful pure wildlife series that didn't mention the environment at all, in a commercial world, where even BBC is affected by commercial things because those programmes sell internationally, you would make a commercial decision to go for the most successful types of programmes – successful, as in more people saw them. They weren't more successful in terms of having environmental effect, they were more successful just in 'bums on seats'. That's one way of measuring whether a programme has an impact, but it's not the only way of measuring it. And I think that you're right, if it put people off commissioning programmes which do both, which could be visually spectacular, engaging with great storytelling and have an environmental benefit too, then we've lost something by not being brave enough to go down that line again. I think that really is

something I miss. It has barely happened at all. In the last 15 years I can't think of any except very recently; for example, *Seven Worlds: One Planet* started to do it - one of the programs that we worked on together. The *Our Planet* series that Netflix showed, that Silverback [Films Ltd] made, was a bit like that too. It's starting to happen, but it is taking an awful long time to get to that stage...to be seen as something that people want to commission.

Commissioning programmes which include environmental issues

JA: Perhaps we could talk about the commissioning process, because how the films are made is structural and it affects what they are about. So, there is a process which we all understand, which is that you rarely pay for your own film to be made - someone else pays for it, which means you have to persuade them to pay for it, which means you have to pitch an idea to a commissioner usually, who's got the cheque book and who will decide whether or not they want the film. Fredi, you have done that more than I have and more than Rowan has, but it sounds like if you suggest an environmental idea overtly, a programme about the environment and harm happening to it, it's a turn off. It's not something that commissioners particularly want to want to pay for it. Would that be a thing, even now, do you think?

FD: In my experience, yes.

JA: Do you sense any sense of change at all in that? Is there any hope in that direction, that the commissioning people, the gate-keepers really, are starting to think that maybe the public does want to hear this?

FD: I think what's interesting is there is a long chain in the BBC down from the very top, down to the Development Office in the Natural History Unit, that pitches the ideas to the commissioners, then the commissioners have two bosses above them. And you just need one person to show some resistance to an idea about an environmental issue, and the whole chain is blocked. With ideas, one negative voice can stop a whole idea from happening, even if the others are positive, because there are large sums of money involved and at the moment people think there's a risk involved, so they might turn away from it.

So, my feeling is that in the upper echelons of the BBC there is a real desire to have more contemporary pieces from the Natural History Unit, making wildlife films that talk about actual issues. I think that within the Natural History Unit there are people that have spent their whole careers, spanning many decades, being extremely successful in taking audiences

to wild places and seeing wild animals as if no human has had any impact on them whatsoever, so I think it's very hard for them to re-envisage their work to take audiences to a bleak place, to a place where animals are suffering, where whole habitats are being destroyed or collapsing. Because it seems very alien, and I understand that, I really do understand that. I think there's a very, very strong cycle of denial in society at large about ecocide - about the deaths of so many habitat and the risk to us, and that's very interesting in itself, and I think in this day and age, it's very difficult for anyone to really know what the truth is out there. We are all in our own echo-chambers. Right now I am suffering from reading far too much about disasters happening to the natural world and at times I get real anxiety from it, and I really have to pace myself with that, but at times I have to question myself - are all my feeds just telling me about the bad things and maybe someone else's feed is telling them about all the wonderful stories from the natural world. It is very difficult to know whose reality is it is, right? Except that there is a vast amount of literature talking about the problems the natural world is facing from humanity right now, so I think that is pretty undeniable, but how you deal with that emotionally; how important and urgent that feels is hard to assess, and I don't really know what to do with regards to the denial aspect of it because that seems like a big hurdle to overcome.

JA: You and I share that don't we Rowan, the idea that the programmes, by omitting the bigger picture, are actually dishonest? In fact, they are painting a picture of the world that doesn't exist.

RA: Misleading I'd say, yes, definitely.

Fredi, would you say that there's a possibility that the rate of change within the BBC, from people being in denial and wanting to show wilderness, and having successfully shown wilderness for so long as a selling point; do you think that a change towards showing what is actually happening and showing destruction and extinction could ever happen as fast as the extinction is happening itself?

FD: The simple answer to that is, it needs to happen very, very fast, just to stop the extinction of one more species, which is a terrible loss in itself.

What seems very regrettable is that in the last 15 years there could have been lots of experimentation on how to achieve large audiences and raise the alarm. I will just tell you briefly about a film that I've worked on recently, and that's *Planet Earth II 'Cities'*.

We had a sequence in that with hawksbill turtle hatchlings. Their eggs are hatched inside the sand. They should climb out of the sand and head straight towards the light of the moon reflected on the water, but because the city lights from the town at the back of the beach are on, a huge amount are disorientated. They head into the town.

I had lots of conversations with my team about that sequence as all it was saying was that there's a massive problem with the urban environment for animals with regard to light pollution. There was no happy ending to that story. We went to film them being disorientated – they don't magically make it out of there, they die in their thousands. There are volunteers that collect them at night and take them back to the sea but the big picture is that it is a disaster for them. That went through lots and lots of iterations of discussions with the people above me, as to whether people were coming to *Planet Earth II* to see a sequence like that, or whether it would be a massive turn off. In the end I think it was celebrated as the sequence within the episode, and the risk paid off, I think.

When I look at that episode now I think we could have had more places within the film where we were more hard-hitting about the issue that animals face in the urban environment, but at the time it was very hard work to get just the turtle sequence in.

We went on to talk broadly about urban sprawl and problems for wildlife.

The next film I worked on was the Antarctica episode of *Seven Worlds: One Planet*. There were two major issues the team wanted to raise around wildlife in Antarctica and the struggles they are facing – one was climate change and the second was whaling - what whaling had done to these incredible creatures in the Southern Ocean. We included climate change with the story around the grey-headed albatross that, John, you filmed exquisitely. You managed to capture a character-based story when we see a chick get blown off its nest and not able to get easily back on its nest, because the winds are stronger because of climate change. It hasn't happened very often in evolutionary history that chicks are being blown off their nests, so they are up on these high nests that keep them dry from the melting snow and rain, but that makes it very, very difficult for them to get back on. Lots of chicks are now being blown off.

What we really wanted in that episode was a story about climate change that was unexpected; you normally just hear about melting ice and sea levels rising and that feels like very important information, but less emotional, so we wanted an emotional piece where you could see that animals are suffering in a surprising way; individual animals are suffering

because of the burning of fossil fuels in countries miles away. We wanted to raise that and we wanted to raise the issue of whaling, so what we engineered, in the structure of that episode, was a double dip; first you are talking about grey-headed albatross being on the road to extinction, and then we talk about whaling and what that did to the great whales in the Southern Ocean, massively reducing their numbers, and we ended the film, I hope, in a hopeful manner, by talking about the return of the great whales, which is not only good for the whales themselves but for the whole ecosystem because of the ecosystem services they provide.

Hope versus despair

FD: I think that for the next film I am working on, the big question going round in my head is how do you end a film? The ban on hunting whales is a great thing; not only great for them - it's also good for the krill stock and it's great for reversing climate change, but can you end a film that you hope will be seen by one billion people around the world, in a way which is not hopeful, but which is more a call to arms?

I think the big thing there is that *Planet Earth III*, the series I am currently working on, is not an overtly environmental-based series. The audience that come to it are not thinking 'I am going to hear about environmental issues', they are coming to it thinking 'I am going to hear about the natural world', so I think that as documentary-makers we must give the whole picture, but how do you end it? You've got to be aware that children are going to be watching this and my current feeling is that the ideal ending to the episode I am working on would be the feeling of a call to arms; not that you feel despair, not that you feel there is no hope, that it's all over - but there's a feeling of outrage at what is happening, and a feeling that 'I need to do something about this'. I think that's a very difficult thing to do but I think it is something that we all have to strive towards; not all of us, but many more of the films need to do that. I think hopeful endings can be very inspiring as well.

RA: ...'stubborn optimism' is a phrase I really like.

JA: ...not giving up.

FD: Rowan, what do you think about a film ending in despair?

RA: I have been reading about the psychology of what we think and why we think it. Again, and again, it says that people won't act out of despair, which I think is true. You can't just say to people that it all is going wrong. I am a big believer in a form of words, pictures, music

- it might be different for each of us - but for each of us there will be a combination that inspires action, and I don't know if that is rooted in despair. I think it is probably not, but I think that if you do not have sense of dread and urgency instilled in you through the film, then I think we've failed because it is dreadful and it is urgent.

JA: Do you think a film can go from being beautiful and engaging about an animal, like the albatrosses, all the way through to explaining to people not just that they need to act but what they can do, or is that too big a canvas for one type of programme, of whatever type of programme it is; just such a big span in an hour, or six hours if it was series, to get from what the world is like and what's happening, all the way through to 'now get up out of your chair and go and do this, this and this to make a difference'?

FD: That's a really good question and something we are looking at all the time with regard to whether we end with solutions. My feeling is that it depends on how complex the problem is. Plastic waste in the ocean is very easy to imagine, and how to stop it. The fourth episode of *Blue Planet II* ends on a mother whale dragging around its dead calf, and the possibility that that calf died from plastic from the oceans was speculated. There was no need a follow-up piece to say 'right, can you now petition supermarkets to use less plastic, can government tax plastic, can we make it a taboo?'. I remember watching that with my two daughters and both of them stood up at the end of the episode and pointed at the screen and said loudly, 'we have to do something!' That was a great example of them feeling the call to arms to do something about plastic pollution. It was very easy then to look at the solutions.

Solutions and action

FD: I think it is harder with more complex issues, climate change being one of them, to know what's more important, to buy an electric car or become a vegan; what's going to do more? What does a flight to the US actually mean? One study I read said that one flight to New York is equivalent to one square metres of Arctic ice disappearing, in a long-term trend (London Heathrow to New York [LINK](#)). One passenger; 3.3 square metres each time they fly. I thought that was really brilliant because I envisage a polar bear having that much less ice to stand on. There's a very visual way of describing climate change and aviation and flights. It's a difficult question because you want inspiring messaging about what can be done, but how much of your programmes do you dedicate to solutions? In *Planet Earth III* it's

important to invite a large audience. You want the audience to think that this is going to be a real treat, and that treat can be an emotional journey. Lots of people go to the cinema to see dramas where they expect they are going to cry, but they love those films. They go and they are going to be blown away by the awe and wonder and the magic of the natural world, and within it are going to learn more about it and the pressures it's facing

JA: So maybe the trick is to have those awe and wonder and story and emotional elements within the context of the bigger picture, which includes what we are doing to the natural world and to link the programme, not *within* the programme, but to link the programme as strongly as we possibly can to other programmes out there, and to NGOs and individuals, or companies, or governments, where there is action happening that people can join in with, so that, if people are primed from having been moved, by plastics for instance, they are not just left unencouraged. They don't have to work it out for themselves, they don't have to become an expert on plastic recycling. They are a motivated person who can be guided to buy less plastic, or to dispose of it more responsibly; but we don't join up because we are making programmes as documentary-makers, so we don't seek to make them actually work, these programmes, to join them to the people who are making a difference, and we could. Your turtle example was a good example because when that went out, I know the digital team were ready – it was in Barbados wasn't it? – so the Barbados turtle rescue people have an organisation, and they accept donations and have volunteers and all that, so even people living in Barbados, having seen that tweet put out as the programme was going on, within minutes of the turtles appearing on the screen, and everybody was thinking 'rescue the turtles!' and the tweet said that the team put down their cameras and rescued the turtles, and there's a bunch of people in Barbados who do this every night and you can support them, here's their website. It was the most popular tweet of the entire series of *Planet Earth II*, as I understand it, which is good in terms of success for the organisation - that's a measure of success. In terms of turtles it's probably a measure of success as well, as I imagine more donations were made and more people volunteered, and probably more turtles were pulled out of drains. But we don't do that as a coordinated thing usually do we? It's quite rare to have that level of coordination, but it could be a routine thing.

FD: That's a very good point. The turtle rescue charity got more donations and volunteers and they did really benefit from that and the turtles did benefit from that. The thing about

that is that we also made a behind-the-scenes web short film, a three-minute film, on the turtle project and we put that on the [series'] programme page.

We have done that with you too, John, talking about grey-headed albatrosses with one of the scientists that you worked with ... but the question is, 'is it enough?' And the answer is 'nowhere even close', when you consider the amount of effort and the budget we spend over four years on making a series like *Seven Worlds: One Planet*, and you think that at the end of Antarctic [episode], you've got two big environmental issues being addressed; whaling and climate change. How are we following up on those topics?

We kind of, I suppose, hope that everyone else will follow up on it, the press will follow up on it, and then it's over. Are we in touch with the NGOs to enough to say the programme is coming out, expect this, get ready, let's co-ordinate? No. That takes up lots of time and the BBC also has to be very careful about impartiality, so for example with the Barbados sea turtle project we had to make sure that other sea turtle projects around the world were also going to benefit from this increased attention.

JA: So that turns the film into a resource for doing more than entertainment, essentially, doesn't it? It takes documentary information about the world; it takes it out and makes it work in a way that a casual watcher is probably unable to do for themselves. They don't have the knowledge or the means to do that. It's re-purposing the stories, the footage, the research, the information, for that other use, essentially. It's interesting because PBS, the [US] public service broadcasting, it's GBH I think, the Boston-based one, does exactly that; they make programmes, show them on the television, then they break them down, make clips, write material around them and make them available to schools. They have done that for decades. It's packaged to fit the curriculum and of course it's fresh and it's interesting because it's visual and it's well-presented, and it fits into lesson plans. It's a great resource and of course the educational establishments are not doing that - they don't have the resources ... so it makes a very good useful free resource for teachers, and I think it's very widely used. There are licensing issues for copyright aren't there?

If you want to persuade people of the need to be environmentally conscious into the future you would start with children really, and very soon they become voters and they are buying things and deciding where they are going to go on holiday, and what sort of diet they want, and all the rest of it; what sort of impact they are going to make on the world. It's a good basis for change. It's not perhaps quick enough, but it's robust.

FD: John, do you remember the BBC doing that before?

JA: I think it did use to happen but it may have been informal, it may have been just teachers video-recording programmes. The Open University certainly reuses and even co-funds programmes, doesn't it? And then [it] has access to the footage and shows whole episodes, but it also makes lessons from the material from programmes quite frequently, I think.

FD: I think the idea is that if you are interested in sealions you can go to a database and find all the BBC sequences that have looked at sealions, so it's a huge educational resource.

Illustrating environmental threats

JA: One thing you said earlier, Fredi, which I was really struck by, is that the difficulty with some of these issues is illustrating them. It's actually quite difficult to find a way to show some of the impacts of climate change, for instance, you can look for skinny polar bears and you might find one swimming where there is no ice, and explain that there are no seals and that's why it's looking for ice, as that's where the seals will be - it can't catch seals in open water - but it's quite difficult, they are few and far between, and the skinny ones are often going to die quite soon. What you are trying to document is something dwindling, which makes them rarer. A maxim of [filmmaking] and writing is 'show doesn't tell', isn't it? The albatross story was a very visual story, films are visual vehicles, aren't they?

We need to demonstrate something to people in a way that's completely convincing because it's true that something is happening, and finding those stories is quite hard; it's actually harder, the more abstract, the more esoteric, the more long-term those problems are; the more difficult it is to find a visual way of doing it. You don't want to film smoke stacks and icebergs and say the world's changing, not if you can help it, you want to find some gripping story that tells that.

FD: I think that's a fair summary and also there are so many complicated issues right now; with polar bears right now. With seals, the ice is so thin they are not able to make the little caves to have their pups protected in, within the ice, so a lot of the seals are giving birth on the sea ice and that's where the pups remain, so in certain areas the polar bears are doing really well because they can catch the seal pups more easily than they could ten years ago. That's because of climate change, but it just means that in twenty year's time their prey base will be much lower and they will have less ice to walk on, and a lower prey base, much

lower - but right now it looks OK. I think that's a very specific example of how it can be complex, and with these changing times, if our industry doesn't change, it may be looking for a lot of success stories. In the 'Cities' episode of *Planet Earth II*, I was looking for animals that are doing well in cities, and, as a balance, the proportion that are doing well in cities as opposed to those that are doing terribly because of urban sprawl is a tiny minority, but the Cities episode doesn't give that perfect balance; it talks about the surprising, extraordinary success stories, with some examples of disaster stories which hopefully are conveying big concepts, but it's not overall giving a balance, in a scientific manner at all.

Does the absence of environmental information suggest to audiences that all is well?

FD: And what we were talking about earlier - it would be very interesting to know whether people that watch a wildlife film that has no environmental issues in it, whether there is a difference before and after, in whether they think the pressures on the natural world are less or the same.

JA: Yes, so if you watch a film that's got no environmental context, just pretty wildlife, do you subliminally receive the view that the world is fine and that there is no need to act on the world not being fine, if you [were to] hear that from other sources? Are we actually being completely counter-productive, by producing these visions of a world that used to be, which is now vanishingly rare ... Are we doing a disservice? Is it actually a lie to do that, because it doesn't represent most of the world at all?

FD: I think that would be a fascinating study; to give viewers a questionnaire on what they think the state of the world is, and then watch a wildlife film and that wildlife film have no environmental issues in it, some environmental issues in it, or be entirely about environmental issues, and then give them another questionnaire afterwards, and ask them what they think the state of the natural world is. You would expect that if they have heard about environmental issues, that they would think the state of the natural world is worse off, but if they've had no environmental issues raised, and if they think after watching that that the natural world is in a better place, then that's very worrying.

That comes back to your very first point, have we failed? You would have to say yes, we have done a disservice to the natural world. That would be incredibly sad for a lot of wildlife filmmakers who were very much hoping to inspire and remind people to fall in love with the natural world.

Are we giving a false impression that all is well?

Not wanting to turn anyone off the genre of wildlife filmmaking, I mean let's go back to the start of wildlife filmmaking: the French have a good industry of making wildlife films and so do the Americans, but one man, Sir David Attenborough, is hugely responsible for wildlife films being so popular all around the world, I would say. So, through making films, you could then argue that with a second wave coming about; with *Blue Planet* and *Planet Earth II* reaching huge numbers of people around the world, that this has engaged a lot more people in the natural world. Has that connected a lot of people to the natural world, or has it given the false sense that everything is OK with the natural world?

JA: Well, it may be true that both things have happened, that more people are connected and possibly more people think it's fine, when really it is becoming much less fine all the time. Then there's the other thing which is whether it makes a difference when people watch a film. Do they actually act differently afterwards, or could they be persuaded to act differently afterwards...?

Rowan, what do you think about that, because you feel very strongly don't you that we must not carry on giving the impression that everything is OK?

RA: Yes definitely, that's the wrong thing to do because we know for sure that it's not OK. My question would be more, when we are saying that [the natural world] is not OK, do people feel a responsibility that it is landing at their feet, or [do they feel that] 'it's not OK, but we can't do much about it'? There is a difference between saying, 'it's not OK, and you were part of causing it to be as it is now', and: 'it's not OK - we should do better'.

What is needed now is not so much a rejigging of the format, or increasing the percentage of the film that talk about environmental issues, but for each episode to be focused around specific environmental issues. It doesn't need to be, 'this is the deforestation episode so we're only going to talk to you about deforestation and show deforestation', but during that hour all the stories are linked to shrinking forests. Through that hour you can start with some stories about forests and make people fall for them, and then slowly it needs to introduce an aspect of 'they are going and it's caused by you, and your habits, in these ways, we are causing this destruction, and it's not just because you're eating soy or whatever, it's because of this whole bigger system'. It needs to be so finely explained to people that there's no way they can say 'we didn't know, we weren't aware that this was happening',

because that's not an excuse anymore. We can't expect people to go and look for these facts themselves, they need to be delivered in a package that they'll not be deterred by.

I think people really do want to know.

JA: So, to be entertained and to learn that in the same programme?

RA: Yes, as Fredi was saying, lots of people go and see thrillers and watch movies with the expectation that their emotions are going to be played with, that's why we go to cinema and watch blockbusters, so to go to something and have your heartstrings pulled and to feel a visceral attachment to a place, an ecosystem, a thing we have now, and then have it explained - and the emotions that go with that - that you, the person watching, is destroying this, as part of seven billion people. I don't think it's a turn-off anymore. I don't think it's something that people say, 'alright, I'm never going to watch a *Blue Planet II* again'.

Urgency

RA: I think that's changed so rapidly - in the last three years - that programme-makers haven't a hope of keeping up. They haven't got the feedback loop to tell them that is has happened, that we need to be not just tweaking the formula but changing the types of programmes we are making drastically, in this next wave of programmes, not in five years' time...

JA: Because they take four or five years to make...

RA: ...because they take so long to make, and in five years' time the chance of us reversing 1.5°C degrees [warming] is so slim. We are almost beyond what we can actually do.

JA: So, are we talking about programmes as a potential solution, when it's actually already too late for these long-term programmes to do anything anyway, because they are so slow to get to that point?

RA: It's really getting to that stage. Where does it cross over to investigative journalism, where you are actually reporting on something that is happening now ... and you are getting the feedback out there quickly? There's much less emotion because we have much less time for those types of programmes.

JA: Fredi is right about David Attenborough (**RA:** definitely) because he is speaking out now all the time, we see him frequently on the news, even talking to parliament, or parliamentary committees, at Davos.

RA: But it would feel wrong, I think, to go and film something happening now, say if we were in Siberia filming wildfires and it's a whole year's carbon budget gone from those fires, whatever it is, a massive amount of carbon released and the methane; huge problems in the Arctic at the moment; It would feel wrong to be filming that and knowing that [the programme] wouldn't be released until 2023, because we can't wait until 2023 for people to be hearing that message and thinking, 'right we've got to do something about this'. It's too long a wait.

FD: I'm in exactly that position right now. There is an environmental issue that I really want to cover in the human episode for *Planet Earth III*, and what I'm really desperately trying to do is engage commissioning in the BBC, to do a one-hour programme on what we will film next year, and get it out within three months of the shoot, but it's challenging because I've got to persuade my bosses that when it comes out in *Planet Earth III*, it will feel fresh and engaging, and I won't have...

RA: ...the news hasn't broken already.

JA: ...and you'll have broken the news yourself, almost, in the other programme.

FD: Yes, and [that] I won't have used all the best footage in the documentary that goes out earlier.

RA: It almost needs a *Panorama*, which doesn't feel the same, doesn't look the same.

JA: But fewer people might watch it. You might get so few people that it doesn't have much impact.

Hard-hitting films – how to communicate facts about environmental harm

FD: So, I think we are also talking about commissioning, and what needs to be commissioned. Personally, I think *Extinction – The Facts*, *Climate Change – The Facts* and *A Life on Our Planet* are three fantastic David Attenborough-fronted documentary films, which are very, very powerful and very direct. There's nothing hidden about that. There's no invite; 'come along and we will tell you all about the wonders of the natural world, but also some of the struggles it's facing', it's just 'we're going to tell you about the struggles it's facing'. They are getting good viewing figures, which is amazing, and they are getting engagement. There is a difference. I won't show my 10- and 8-year-old daughters *Extinction - The Facts*. I'm not going to engage them at that age. I am worried about eco-anxiety in young children, whereas I would show them *Blue Planet II* and get them enraged about plastics, and that's

an interesting discussion. My cousin's son age 10, watched the walrus sequence in *Our Planet*, the walrus tumbling off the cliffs. He hasn't watched another wildlife film since then. It's an absolute blanket 'no'; even the Antarctica film we worked on John, even a close relative of his' work for the last 4 years, he won't watch it because of that sequence and it's been a real turn off. I think with young children there's something we have to be mindful of. My view is that gore is dangerous, but you don't need gore for powerful emotions that bring you to a call to arms.

RA: No, it's much more about care and love.

FD: It's a *sense* of the threat, I mean it was used in *Jaws*, you hardly ever saw the shark but you got the sense of the threat, which can be incredibly powerful, and so that's all about the craft. Not diminishing that particular *Our Planet* film, it's very powerful and no doubt it had a positive impact on people making changes, I suspect, but I think it comes back to that in the last 15 years we haven't been experimenting, we haven't been working out what's the best way to communicate environmental issues that are engaging.

JA: Yes, it wasn't the brief, it wasn't what the programmes were asked to do at all. They haven't been tasked with that until, well, not even now really. It's happening a little bit by...stealth would be the wrong word... but it's happening in addition to the brief, so the brief might be for a series about geographical areas or something (they usually are aren't they?) and in those geographical areas certain things are happening, and if there are major things, like deforestation in [the] Asia [episode] in *Seven Worlds: One Planet*, then it would be remiss not to include that. The *Seven Worlds: One Planet*, Asia episode did major on deforestation, some of the time.

RA: My question is can we afford to do both? Can we actually, in good conscience, say 'we are going to make programmes like *Extinction – The Facts*, in one arm of the BBC, and this is destruction and we're causing it', and [also] make the nice middle-ground ones, which are going to be *Blue Planet II*, *Planet Earth III*, drawing [large] audiences and talking about it a bit, and make some that just don't mention it at all. In making *Extinction - The Facts*, surely you've sold your licence to make the ones that don't talk about it at all?

JA: It is part of the function of a public service broadcaster to not just look at the audience figures, you mean?

RA: I mean, if you were the same person making all three, you couldn't make the ones that don't mention extinction, after making *Extinction - The Facts*. You've stepped down there,

having said, 'we believe this, we believe this so much we are going to make an hour-long documentary on it, with the same guy that narrates everything else, and now we're going to show you some cute animals and show you how prosperous they are, and don't worry about it', and that's going to be on a week later, just 'forget what we told you'.

FD: I totally agree with you Rowan, I don't think it's right to be making wildlife films that don't in some way address environmental issues now. Have you seen *My Octopus Teacher*?

JA & RA: Not yet.

FD: It's absolutely brilliant. Now that is a film, a wildlife film, about connection to nature, and connecting with an animal - very, very inspiring. Does it talk about the plight of the octopus and the plight of the kelp forest it's living in? Very little. It just says at the end, that the key human character in the film is now dedicating his time to protecting that kelp forest, but it doesn't talk about the threats or anything, however it is a very, very good film in showing how human mental health can be massively enriched from the natural world and, I think that's a very interesting film that some people would say is not banging on about environmental issues, and yet it totally is. It is totally talking about the nub of what all our environmental issues are, which is the connection to the natural world, and right at the heart of it, the lead character is talking about how he first filmed the San bushmen hunting antelope in Southern Africa, and how they were not apart from nature, they were *in* nature; how so much of our lives are apart from nature, and ultimately everything that we do which is harming the natural world is ignorance and lack of care.

Films about personal relationships with nature

JA: That's an interesting example Fredi, because that's a film about a person and their relationship with nature, a different genre almost of films, aren't they, where by that person's sincerity and the clear truth that there is nothing made up about what they are saying? It completely comes over, I imagine, in the film, that it's real? You believe the sincerity of another human when it's transparent like that, and vicariously you inherit that relationship with that octopus, and with nature in that kelp forest, and that can be very moving and it can change people's minds, like the Chris Jordan film, *Albatross*, where you can't fail to be moved by his commitment to those birds. He is dreadfully upset by what's happening when they have swallowed plastic and it kills the chicks, and you come away from that film changed I think. They have a central human character, which is very different

from a narrator isn't it? It's a different kind of effect really, you're receiving less information and receiving more emotion from a person.

FD: Yes, and we can do that within our landmark films as well, in sequences, I think.

JA: Where you associate with an individual animal instead of talking about populations or species or biological processes. You say, 'this individual here is in trouble for this reason, look what happens'.

FD: Yes, character-based stories and also human-based stories that reveal a connection.

JA: That's rare, isn't it, for our type of programmes that we often make together? These pure wildlife film hardly ever have a human in them, it's very unusual.

FD: It's very rare to hear their voice.

The other thing I've been thinking about Rowan, when you've been talking, is who is the audience and that's important.

RA: Yes, so important, and how do we know who the audience are?

Films that have an impact on the audience and beyond

FD: Did you watch *The End of the Line* documentary, about overfishing?

RA: No

FD: So, *The End of the Line* is a very factual documentary about fish stocks and the way we are harvesting from our oceans unsustainably, and I watched it in the cinema and I came out feeling like, I've learned lots and hadn't felt as much as I'd hoped to, going in. I hadn't thought, 'what does it feel like to be a dwindling tuna?' These enormous tuna - can we get into the world of the tuna a little bit before we see it captured, and what does that mean to the tuna that are left behind? And then I spoke to someone who is a friend of the filmmaker. They said that that film was extremely successful. They made the film like an impact producer would make a film, with a budget and with a target around fishing quotas and policy, and they delivered that film to the cinema. I am not sure if it was a financial success or not but they delivered it to ministers, they delivered it to civil servants, and they got it to the audience in a very targeted manner that they wanted to influence, and through that got some policy. That was about informing.

JA: Double informing, because ministers and civil servants were informed *by* the film *and* that an awful lot of people had seen the film - it had a double Impact because they were

aware that loads of potential voters or constituents or whatever, had also received that information from that film. It's quite an interesting ploy isn't it?

FD: And that I think is the power of *Blue Planet II* plastics as well. So many people had seen it that supermarket bosses are suddenly like, 'right, OK, everyone has joined the dots.'

JA: And a cabinet minister phoned up David Attenborough and went to see him the next morning, after that programme with the whale and the dead calf. They watch television too and they know an awful lot of other people watch television. It does make a difference I think, knowing what's out there. Theresa May gave a DVD set of *Blue Planet II* to the Chinese President on a state visit. That's as high stakes as it gets for information being passed around isn't it, where one Prime Minister gives it to a president of another country, and says this is something we do well in Britain and actually we believe in the message of this? It's quite unusual.

Should wildlife films aim to have more real-world impact? If so, how?

FD: I keep coming back to this question of have we failed.

JA: Perhaps we don't know yet. Maybe it's too soon to answer.

FD: When I was doing my PhD there was someone who came to the Cambridge Biology Department; the title of her talk was *Why Conservation Science is Failing*. It was a really powerful talk about: you guys are all doing conservation science and you get funding from NERC and other funding bodies, and you go out you find out there's a really bad thing happening to the natural world and you publish it in a scientific journal that hardly anyone reads. Does it get to any policy decision makers at all? And then you are on to your next project, your next funding and your next publishing deadline. Are you actually having the impact that you're hoping to have? Are the channels in place? Do you, after having published your paper, then have a year to be the impact producer on that paper, or do you have to find your next grant to fund your next piece of work, and that paper goes unread? It was really, really important. Having started in academia and then moved into wildlife filmmaking, a big part of that decision was to reach many more people.

And so, it's a big question as to have we been failing; I think in particular in making these blockbuster landmark series that reach large numbers of people but don't deliver enough on environmental issues and in the fact that there's also a discussion about whether conservation science is being effective. It's all about getting the message out there to large

numbers of people. Some conservation scientists must no doubt be thinking, 'well isn't that your job?'

JA: Yes, we are supposed to be between the scientists and the public.

FD: They say, 'you call us all the time to get stories, can't you put it out there on a wider scale?'

JA: It's a very important thing that, isn't it? We don't find the primary information or analyse it. We receive and read and digest and compress and simplify that mass, in the thousands of papers you must read for each of these episodes that you're producing, and the researchers on the programme; thousands, tens of thousands maybe, of bits of information coming into one hour of television. We know a lot of people watch the programmes, but it's quite a lot to hope that they're taking it away - What will they remember? Three or four things from each programme if we're lucky? – and that they will convert that into doing something as a direct consequence of watching the programme.

It makes far more sense to think that we have primed a large number of people with an interest and a bit of awareness about this topic, or this area, or this species, but for that to become change requires help. It requires coordinated, heavy-duty action to make those viewers into people who are going to do something slightly differently in the future; major differences in the future. It's optimistic to think that television could change the world isn't it? But it's a pretty good medium for passing information and feeling and motivation around. It does seem though that we just stop short and that perhaps it's not picked up by others.

I did see though that *Extinction – The Facts* was quoted a lot, even in the Scottish Parliament. A member of the Scottish Parliament quoted it to the First Minister the other day, and asked 'what are we doing about this?'. He was a Scottish Green Party MSP, so he was inclined to think it matters more, perhaps, than other MSPs. It was batted away, you know, without much response, but they are quoted, these things. We do raise the profile by doing this, which is a starting point, but it would be great to think there was something more that could be done with the fruits of our labours.

FD: So, this comes back to Rowan's point about not rejigging the genre but having a revolution, and rethinking it entirely; thinking about who the audience is, who do you want the change to come from? I think a really good example of a difficult issue for people to raise, for whatever reason, is meat consumption. I find that fascinating. I think it is not disproportionate in these hard-hitting documentaries to say stop eating meat, you can do it,

you can do it from now, it's going to have a massive impact. There are other things, saving up for an electric car, other things, big, big changes, you know, getting insulation in your roof. You can just stop buying meat now, or massively reduce it and your dairy products, and the question of whether there's been reticence about getting that message out, not just from wildlife filmmaking, also from environmental campaign, because they're worried about not getting money, their subscription money from meat eaters. I think that's a really good one, so that's one where you can put it on a mass audience, you can put it and say 'if you want to take responsibility, then this is one thing you can do right now'.

Then there is the other one which is, how do you go to the other end of the spectrum, how do you get the message to the billionaires, to the leaders of the corporations and the leaders of states to say 'why aren't you doing more?'

What I hear from you, Rowan, is being direct about this messaging.

RA: There are two ways that I see this - there's a sort of gateway programme that people click on and get hooked and they see that they're interested, or they become interested and they get whooshed through; and then there's *Extinction – The Facts* which was definitely preaching to the converted but informing people. The two, the three camps that we see as [our] audiences are:

- i. The uninterested, or not particularly looking to be interested;
- ii. people who already know that they should be doing something, and then;
- iii. people who are actively doing something already about it.

And you get all of the actively, 'already doing something about it' people coming to direct programmes like *Extinction – The Facts*, and, you get some people who think they should be doing something coming to *Extinction – The Facts*, but not many ... *Blue Planet II* or *Planet Earth III* will take the people that are really passionate about it and do something actively; they'll take the middle ground people and they'll probably interest the people who don't really care much at all, because they want to be entertained.

I think what we haven't noticed and has changed really, really quickly, is that the camp that don't really care and aren't interested, is down to 2 or 3% of the population, maybe not 3% but maybe 10%, but most people are now in the camp of interest and wanting to do something about it, and they are hovering around, looking at programmes like *Planet Earth III* and saying 'well maybe I shouldn't be as worried as I feel I am?', or maybe [those

programmes] are providing a gateway but the end place then isn't really there, because we haven't made very many programmes like *Extinction – The Facts*.

We don't have to do this all-in-one but it needs to be either really linked up, or we need to broaden out from preaching to people that we already know are making an effort.

Encouraging action

JA: And there's that missing third stage isn't there? We heard from quite a few people who watched *Extinction – The Facts* who said, 'I really wish they'd said what we can do', and television doesn't do that; it hardly ever says what you can do. It doesn't deal with it because it's difficult to say 'don't buy petrol from Exxon', or 'don't eat meat from feedlots'.

RA: Because you then need to say in a different programme, 'eat meat', to keep the balance [because of the broadcaster's need to be impartial].

JA: Because the corporations don't like it if you point the finger.

RA: I think it's wildly difficult to get it all right the first time. We haven't been practicing.

FD: But we can say, 'if you take one flight from London to New York, that's 3.3 square metres [of melted sea ice]. If you eat meat, as a regular US diet, compared to a regular vegan US diet, you have 18 times the footprint of the vegan, in terms of your diet alone' – I don't know if that's factually correct, that was in *Cowspiracy*, but you can, as documentary-makers, just outline the facts and say 'well, this is it'.

RA: You can but I think you need the emotional connection for people to jump from facts to action. I think, for example, just reading a list of fact, nobody changes their behaviour at all. The emotional connection to someone or something has to be played first, before you can start saying, 'this is the one thing that will help the most'. It absolutely has to stop being framed as sacrifice, or a loss to humanity. We can't keep going, 'yes, we know life's going to be less good than it was, but we will get a nicer, cleaner atmosphere, and we won't be toasting'. It needs to be absolutely framed as an opportunity and a logical next stage in human evolution, to make a move to net zero and to run everything off renewables. Even if you looked at it on efficiencies that will be the thing to do. It's the ingrained system and the *status quo* that's stopping this happening, regardless of whether it was good or not for the environment. It's those bigger things. Plastics in the ocean are literally a drop in the ocean, they are a big deal for the ocean but in terms of the changes needed, it's still only a tiny part of what's needed, but that message just doesn't get out there, does it?

FD: That's an interesting one. I've heard someone say that they thought plastics is a distraction from climate change and habitat destruction, and so the politicians are like, 'hey, I'm going to do something green, I'm going to focus on plastics', knowing that they're not doing the important stuff.

JA: ... [instead of] fossil fuels or something.

FD: But I am not convinced by that because I think that when you engage my children for example, in plastic recycling, and less use of plastics, and getting Tupperware that we then go to the health food shop and top up, that engages them with environmental issues, which then leads to more discussions about that, more discussions and more discussions, so I think it's a good thing.

RA: Yes definitely, but I think also, everyone, not only politicians, have found that they can 'get' plastic and understand it and they know exactly why it's doing damage. It's really not a complicated thing to grasp, but if you're a politician and you're thinking about starting a campaign on climate change, you are faced with the same barriers that we are; persuading a lot of people to do something that is really uncomfortable for themselves, something that is invisible for a lot of people. One [poll] that I read recently, said that the countries most concerned with climate change are the ones that are affected most. It's the ones that are already feeling dangerous heat or more frequent storms, or they are actually going underwater. Those are the ones where the whole population is saying '96% of us think this is really serious', whereas places like Norway and Sweden and the UK, have about 12-13% of the whole population thinking that it is really not a big deal and there is nothing much we should be doing about it.

JA: It's not painful enough here.

RA: It's not even here. How often do you go about your day-to-day life and think 'that's a pain, that wasn't the case five years ago because of climate change - this is now a real burden on me, and this has killed my friend or my relative'?

JA: ...flooded my house...

RA: ... we have not got that at all, and our programmes are speaking in those languages, that we are not affected, but if we were making them based in the Marshall Islands, we would be making very different programmes, I am sure of it.

FD: We are reactive, we're not being proactive.

JA: Do you think though, as programme makers, our duty is to be ahead of this, and that the commissioning process should be ahead? It's like politicians; their duty is to be better informed and to lead by telling us uncomfortable truths while there is still time to act, but the programme-makers aren't invited to do this by commissioners because the commissioners' duty is not seen that way. [Television] is seen as an entertainment medium, particularly being something that's measured in terms of audience size and so on, in competition with other channels. It's not really measured in terms of societal benefits at all. That's not its function. It doesn't have to be like that.

You can make your own films and put them on Netflix or in the cinema, or just on YouTube, self-funded and all the rest, and then you can say what you like, and no impartiality required, and no editorial control from anybody else, but of course they can't have the same clout because they don't have the authority of the traditional broadcasters or the budget, or the scope and the range. Moving pictures are much broader than just TV aren't they?

FD: They are. I don't know, I mean, I think *Extinction - the Facts* being on at 8pm on Sunday night, in the best slot in the week, is a sign of the changing times. They backed it, they really, really backed it, and it got very, very high viewing figures, and it got huge attention from the press and I suspect it will win a huge number of awards. I think it's a very, very important film because it's a very clear statement of where we're at. I think once David Attenborough has said it, no politician can say 'I didn't realise', and well, you should be watching what David Attenborough is saying if you want you know about the natural world - that's page one, right? You really should be reading scientific journals and the civil servants should be informing you in greater detail, but at the very basic level, you should at least have that.

So I think it's very exciting that documentaries like that are being made. They can at least hold decision-makers to account. They can't pretend ignorance. I think there are lots of discussions we're in right now. We need more of those. We [also] need more gentle pieces aimed at children, which I think gets into the syllabus. We [also] need to make solution-based films more sexy. I'm sure you watched *2040* – a solution-based film, very optimistic.

RA: Yeah, it was great. No doom and gloom. Lots of optimism but no outrage.

The power of despair

FD: Yeah, no outrage. I'm coming back to the despair point; John how did you feel when you finished watching *Albatross*, the film by Chris Jordan.

JA: I was intensely upset. I could hardly watch it, I was so upset by it, and then I have to separate in my mind, as a programme-maker; I have to watch it with two minds at the same time, so I am watching it, being affected, as a person who hasn't seen it before, an audience member, but I'm also watching it in terms of 'is it effective? Is it doing something?'

And I felt, as the audience member, deeply moved, and as the programme-maker, a bit frustrated that it was so long and so unlikely to be seen by as many people as it would if it was in one of these 8pm slots on a Sunday on BBC One, so it would make a big difference to how people behave.

It's about plastics in the ocean, and about, in the bigger sense, our over-consumption and our waste and our indifference to what happens somewhere else when we do something easy for us, where we live. It did that beautifully, it did that incredibly compellingly, but it's still a niche thing, and it doesn't cut through to most people, because most people won't see it. Even if they started watching it, as soon as it became upsetting they would stop, many people would stop, my mother would stop watching it rather than watch it to the end.

I don't know how we do this and I suspect there is no single answer. I think [the solution must be to make films] across the board, in many, many different ways; simple things for children and hard-hitting things for people who want to know more and are prepared to stick with it, and something very deeply practical that's really easily accessible, maybe comedy or something, for the people ... I mean [let's] pick the most unlikely person; if you can get Jeremy Clarkson talking about something, say saving money by renewable energy or whatever it is...electric cars...then you've made a bigger dent in environmental harm, even though it has come from a quite unlikely direction, than if you were trying to shock people into doing something different.

RA: As someone that cares about it and was moved by *Albatross*, what did you change? What did you do?

JA: Well, I was part-way there already in some ways. It did make some difference, in terms of being absolutely determined that plastic don't go in the sea. I pick up a lot of waste from the beach. Whenever I see anything plastic on the shore I pick it up, and end up festooned with plastic bags when I am walking on the shoreline, and it's spoils the walks in some ways doesn't it? We just don't leave rubbish on the beach, and it's through knowledge of entanglement and animals dying; every plastic bag that you leave on the floor is going to end up in the water and it might be swallowed by a whale or tangling up a bird, or fed to

some young bird somewhere. But I did sort of know that already, but it's definitely... I wouldn't walk past a piece of litter on the beach now at all and I suppose there was a time when I might have done, sometimes, just because it was inconvenient, so it's all been part of an ongoing greater commitment to do something.

I think I have felt that over the last decade really, but in the last three or four years I'm really committed to doing as much as I possibly can in my personal life to change my impacts, and try and make a difference, rather than just making films which previously I thought was enough; to work to make a difference and now I want to make a difference all the time, more and more.

FD: I had a feeling of despair for about 3-4 days after that film.

JA: Hmm, I couldn't get it out of my head.

FD: I was very, very low, very blue, and then I turned it around and I think that's my nature to be optimistic, and proactive, and I think that that was effective for me.

This is one thing I've been exploring, with ending films with despair. I don't think he [Chris Jordan] intended for the film to end with despair, but that certainly was my experience.

I think it can be very powerful if you managed to turn around. That film has stayed with me and it's interesting, my relationship to plastic waste. I think that right now I couldn't do more but I bet I can, and I bet that when I watch something, I'll do something a bit more. There are three films; *Blue Planet II*, *Albatross* and one called *Plastic China* which is documenting how people recycle plastic, and you just realise 'Oh God, recycling plastic is not a wonderful thing for nature'. We just need no plastic, in the way we use it in such a massive way, because it's so toxic, the chemicals, and so many health issues for the Chinese people that were doing it in this filming. So much pollution comes from it, from melting it down. Each time I've watched something like that I do something more with regards to plastic, but what I'm interested in is how it's the despair; that is why I remember that film a lot more than I would other films.

JA: ...and you showed [*Albatross*] to your colleagues at work didn't you, forced yourself to watch it again and showed it to them?

FD: I've watched it three times. And that's great, to watch it again and again. That's good and it's had an impact, but you definitely remember it. The longevity of the film in your conscious mind is massively increased, for me, when I'm left in despair. The risk is, if you don't turn [the despair] around; that's a real problem.

JA: So, [we] have to help people turn it around. You've managed to do that yourself by really caring, but if you were to leave people with that despairing end feeling and not help them find a positive, especially if they don't feel that they know what to do; so [I am] just thinking about your dilemma about how to end the current programme that you're making, whether, unusually for a wildlife film, you could have a person at the end who you trust, to be the one who says 'I am now doing something differently', and the audience would vicariously think, 'and so am I. I am persuaded now because you are, you person I trust, to also act'.

RA: What about, with this kind of despair that we all feel, if we know how to do despair, there's no lack of despair in this at the moment, what about very simply just saying that the future isn't predetermined, it is not a thing that is already decided.

JA: ...we have not yet failed...

RA: That's not, 'you have to go and now stop eating meat', but it is an open-ended question. I feel much more powerful if I am told first 'why' and then, 'this isn't over, it's ongoing, it's not a lost cause'. That's the crucial bit. If you say it's a lost cause and the game is over, the game really is over. It's done.

JA: It's a self-fulfilling prophesy isn't it, if you say it is pointless?

RA: But if you are told ... maybe you don't even need to be told what to do specifically in that moment, but if you're told that nature bounces back and that, leave it be...

JA: ...shown, ideally...

RA: ...yes, shown; I think that's powerful.

Nurturing hope

JA: This also has the really relevant thing, I think, which is also a reason for hope, which is that the youth movements have been absolutely extraordinary in the last few years. Like you were saying, it is extraordinary that *Extinction - the Facts* was on television in the main slot on the BBC; it's also extraordinary that they have been marches attended by tens or even hundreds of thousands of people sometimes, all over the world, who are motivated by teenagers telling them, 'we believe that our leaders are letting us down by not taking this seriously'. It's the most hopeful thing I remember happening in decades, but we mustn't, in our world, in our work, squander that hope by making it too despairing because, if it puts off any of those people, if they think it really is hopeless, then that movement might wither on

the vine and that would be the worst thing, because it's actually the best thing at the moment. We've got to find some way of [our films] being a call to arms rather than being a call to apathy.

FD: Yes.

JA: What do you find hope in, Fredi, in your best moments? What do you think, 'right, this is where we can find some sort of spark, some sort of possibility of making change'?

FD: The things I love most about the world are the natural world. I am fascinated by evolution and the human mind, and so I'm not a human-hater in any shape or form. I think the human consciousness that we've achieved through evolutionary time is extraordinary, and amazes me, and the natural world is spectacular in all its complexity, and so I balance those two, otherwise I think if you just focus on the natural world...so even if there is a development in some really difficult mathematical problem...

JA: (laughs) ...then it's a good thing, it's a success...

FD: ...it could not feel more irrelevant right now that people are dedicating their lives to some theorem, how many more digits to Pi they can work out or whatever, I still think that's so beautiful and so worth celebrating, so I get a lot of hope from all kinds of human ingenuity. And then I get hope from learning more about the natural world. A massive piece of hope that I have had recently is the fact that a whale coming back is equivalent to a forest of 30,000 trees; every whale is like a little forest swimming around, because it's cycling nutrients. We have been in touch with the scientists: The whales come in, they poo, that brings algal blooms that feed the krill in the Southern Ocean and that in turn feeds the whales, so that's important in itself, bring the iron rich poo to the water where the limiting factor is iron for plant growth, but it's the fact that they are cycling, that they are swimming to depths and going to the surface, swimming to the depths, which is mixing the nutrients. That's worth around 28-30,000 trees, causing the phytoplankton bloom, and then they eat the krill and then they are heavy so they take all that carbon down with their bodies when they die, to the bottom of the ocean.

That's amazing in itself, but I love the fact that we protected whales *before* we knew the fact that they are such incredible ecosystem services in terms of sequestering carbon, and the fact that krill stocks in the Southern Ocean are going up since the return of the great whales, so the knowledge that biodiverse ecosystems are resilient and highly productive brings about lots of hope, and with it you recognise that every extinction, potentially, will

lead to collapse, and that's what brings about the urgency. That's what I think we are not communicating.

Communicating the inter-linked complexity of natural systems. The role of presenters

FD: It's one thing to communicate the fires in California and link it to climate change; it's another to do what the film *The Serengeti Rules* does. It talks about how the hunting of the great whale took away food from the orcas that were hunting whales, and those orcas decimated the seal populations and then turned on to sea otters, in the Aleutian Islands, which led to the sea urchins eating all of the kelp forest and suddenly the whole system collapses; so you've got these really long domino effects, of one impacting the other over very big distances, and livelihoods of people just disappearing, as well as full system collapse. It's that idea that the world is very, very small and we are all interconnected.

RA: And we don't know half of it. We could mess with the wrong bit and it would just go wrong.

FD: I am trying to get that interconnectivity story out there.

JA: Yes, that's the 'show don't tell' bit isn't it? It's harder to show that than it is to tell it.

FD: So, we need more presenter-led programmes.

JA: Maybe we do, with people that we really care about, who are completely sincere, who persuade us. Perhaps that is where it should go next?

FD: John, over your working career you have gone from David Attenborough fronting the programmes that you're working on, less and less and less.

JA: Yes, he's just narrating now really isn't he, and sort of top-and-tailing the programmes, but he is 94.

FD: Before, he was explaining what was going on in the natural world to a greater extent.

JA: ...and people loved it, people were thrilled to see him talking to mole rats or with the gorilla sitting on him. It feels like it hasn't happened for a while.

FD: There is greater sales potential once you take David out, you can get a different narrator and sell it all around the world with a different language narrator. Whereas, with David in, it just goes to English-speaking countries. That could be one of the reasons why we've seen that.

JA: Yes, it's a commercial thing, partly, isn't it?

Parting thoughts

JA: Fredi, you are so insightful, you have so many examples and you have thought about this so carefully. Thank you very much indeed. You really are just a wonderful person to talk to about this because it feels to us such an important thing, and it feels like it's on a cusp really, it could go either way just now. There is potential for the work that we really believe in to make a substantial difference, or to become largely irrelevant, if it carries on documenting down to the last individual animals. I think we are part of a large group, an increasing group of people, who feel that there needs to be more reflection of how the world actually is in the films we are making, and that the public actually wants to see those films too. So let's hope that that's what happens.

I think you are at the cutting edge of it really, in terms of making these films in that way, which are still entertaining and informative and have this extra dimension of persuading people that there is a need to behave differently. I really admire what you are doing and I think you've made a big difference.

FD: Well exactly the same to both of you, but also what I think we come back to is the measure of success. I remember going to a talk by Jane Goodall, who was studying the behaviour of chimpanzees, and then realised that if she was going to have the opportunity to study chimpanzees, she needed to protect them. As wildlife filmmakers we have to think exactly the same way, and I would like the future series to put less emphasis of success on audience numbers and more on how much of the natural world is being protected. If we have to frame that in a selfish, 'longevity of livelihood' framework, so be it. I would rather have more of 'this is the right thing to do'.

JA: Yes, and to be up front about it, to say that 'we have made a conscious decision with this programme to include the context, and it's the first time we've done this and we are doing it for this reason, and we hope you'll stick with us, because we think it's important.'